

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D7.2: Dissemination Pack

WP7 – Dissemination

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1 Executive summary

Deliverable D7.2 “Dissemination pack” provides an overview of the STEP project website, the first leaflet of the project, the first issue of the project newsletter, and a promotional video. It also provides a “snapshot” of the website at the time of writing this document (November 2015).

The STEP website (<http://step4youth.eu/>) constitutes the primary platform of the project’s communication activities, as:

- it is the main communication gate with the project target groups, promoting relevant activities and events,
- it is used as the main information repository of the project, and
- it supports the internal communication and management of the consortium.

Apart from “static” contents (i.e. project description), the project website includes “dynamic” areas where relevant news and announcements for events are regularly released. All partners contribute to the content creation and update.

The dissemination material described in the current deliverable comprised:

- A first version of the project leaflet that provides essential information about STEP in a double sided three-folded A4 paper.
- The first issue of the project semi-annual newsletter.
- A first version of a promotional video with general project information.

2 STEP Website

The STEP website serves as the project’s main dissemination tool and will be updated on a regular basis. The goal of the STEP website is twofold. On the one hand, it will be used as a dissemination tool among the STEP interested audience by providing information on the project’s activities, progress and outcomes (public section). On the other hand, it will be also used as a management tool among the project partners by offering access to all documentation and deliverables produced in the course of the project (STEP Partners Area).

Furthermore, the website will advertise the project to potential users and relevant stakeholders such as young people; local, regional and national authorities; stakeholders involved in the decision making procedures for youth and environment; NGOs; and project partners. The technical implementation of the STEP website has been the product of collaboration among several professionals in the field including graphic designers, web developers and media experts. The current version of the STEP website follows the project’s graphical identity and presents a project overview, including objectives, project partners and the activities proposed within the project. The project website serves as a central point of entry to all public material, such as public deliverables, reports, newsletters, dissemination material (brochures, leaflets and posters), presentations and promotional videos developed as part of the project.

2.1 Website Requirements

The conceptual and technical realisation of the STEP website requires a set of specific requirements to be met. These requirements originate from contractual agreements such as the Grant Agreement, the existence of different target groups and stakeholders relevant to the project as well as requirements related to gender equality. In the following paragraphs these requirements are described along with the way they were incorporated in the STEP project website.

2.1.1 Requirements from Grant Agreement

According to Article 29 “Dissemination of Results – Open Access – Visibility of EU funding” of the project’s Grand Agreement (p. 48) and especially article 29.4 “Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem”, any dissemination results in any form, including electronic, must a) display the EU emblem and b) include the following text: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493”. It is also noted that when displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

In order to meet the above requirement the above text and EU emblem has been placed in a prominent position in the footer of all website pages in order to properly acknowledge the information of EU funding.

2.1.2 Requirements from target groups and relevant stakeholders

The STEP website is the project’s main dissemination tool. Therefore it has been designed in order to meet the requirements set by the target groups and stakeholders related to the topic of the project (young people; local, regional and national authorities; stakeholders involved in the decision making procedures for youth and environment; NGOs; and the general public). The pages of the website were designed in order to provide the needed information and material in a way easily understood by all the target groups and stakeholders.

2.1.3 Gender requirements related to website construction and development

The STEP consortium has committed at an early stage of the project to actively promote gender equality and pay the relevant attention to gender aspects and issues during the project implementation. For that reason certain requirements have to be met in order for the STEP website to be gender neutral and fulfil the provisions for equality among women and men for maximising the impact that the website has as a central dissemination tool.

Gender biases exist and are deeply ingrained in many of the modern technologies and practices such as internet and website design. This is a logical result since computer and IT sciences are being dominated by male scientists and developers. This prevalence of male IT professionals and developers has resulted in the current majority of websites being dominated by the so called “male design aesthetic”^{1,2,3}. Such a fact can

¹ Moss G., Gunn R., Kubacki K., 2008. Gender and web design: The implications of the mirroring principle for the services branding model. *Journal of Marketing Communications* , 14 (1), 37-57.

² Simon S. J., 2000. The impact of culture and gender on web sites: an empirical study. *ACM SIGMIS Database*, 32 (1), 18-37.

³ Barth, Derrick. *Designing the Gender-Neutral User Experience*. Diss. WORCESTER POLYTECHNIC INSTITUTE, 2012.

have a significant impact on female users' experience and participation while at the same time research has shown that in many cases men and women have different preferences in the layout design of a web portal, site or application⁴. User Experience, within the context of the STEP website and other dissemination material, refers to how a person feels about using a product, system, or service.

The visual representation of information on the screen affects user's perception and processing of that information, whereas the colour, layouts, and language affect user's impression of a website interface. Psychological and evolutionary studies have suggested a difference in how women and men see and process information. Notable examples are in colour, word usage, and shapes which, either due to genetic or psychological reasons, are perceived differently by individuals of different gender. There are distinct elements in website interface design that will be preferred by either men or women, and websites can be made to specifically target one gender using these principles.

According to specific research on gender and web design^{5,6}, the most common male and female biases in web design fall into the following categories:

- Language. Men typically use more professional, assertive speech whereas women tend to be more conversational and less formal by employing abbreviations and by using non-expert and informal language.
- Colour. One of the main areas where women and men have shown a significant statistical difference is colour. Men tend to use less variation in colour and lean toward grayscale, or only dark, cool colours. Women use much more colour, including brighter ones such as white, yellow, pink, and mauve. Moreover women often use informal colourful typography.
- Layout and data structure. Men have a tendency to design with rigid, less rounded edges and organise data in condensed rows. Women avoid a horizontal layout, use rounded rather than straight shapes and design with more organic, amorphous shapes, and display data in wide, spread out areas.

According to literature the essential elements of a gender neutral website are:

- Nature imagery in background and present throughout interface.
- Rounded corners, but less so than a female biased interface.
- Minimal language use, and in a casual but non-conversational tone when in use. It is obvious that special care must be taken to the use of gendered language.
- A mix of widely placed content but in a vertical scrolling area in browser friendly fields.

Further elements of a gender neutral website related to colour are:

⁴ Djasasbi S., Tullis T., Hsu J., Mazuera E., Osberg K., Bosch J., 2007. Gender preferences in web design: usability testing through eye tracking. Proceedings of the Thirteenth Americas Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS).

⁵ Moss, G., Gunn, R., & Heller, J. (2006). Some men like it black, some women like it pink: consumer implications of differences in male and female website design. *Journal of Consumer behaviour*, 5(4), 328-341.

⁶ Moss, G. A., Gunn, R., & Kubacki, K. (2007). Successes and failures of the mirroring principle: the case of angling and beauty websites. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 31(3), 248-257.

- The use of strong contrasts between any background colour and the overlying text.
- Background behind text solid and plain.
- One dominant colour in headings and borders with bright tones are better.
- Visual interest can be provided with contrast colours complementary or closely related to the website dominant colour.
- Colours that closely relate to primary or secondary colours when possible can be selected.
- Colour elements such neon, pastel, dark, discordant, or unusual should be avoided.

Using the above elements, the STEP website attempts to overcome and go beyond any existing gender norm by providing an innovative website interface design that includes a synthesis between male- and female-targeted interface designs in order to provide a gender neutral user experience.

However, it has to be noted that even if much care and attention is given to this topic, there is no single recipe in approaching gender issues that have an inherent subjective aspect. Before going online, the STEP website design has been assessed both by male and female professionals. Further assessment of the website design will be provided during the project implementation and the appropriate modifications will be applied when and where needed.

2.2 Website structure

The STEP website (www.step4youth.eu) is comprised of the following sections:

- Home
- About STEP
 - Project description
 - Background & objectives
 - What are we doing?
- About us
 - Partners
 - Advisory Board
- Pilots
- Download area
 - Deliverables
 - Dissemination material
- Useful links
- News
- Contact
- Partners Area

2.3 Content

The STEP website includes a brief description of the project's scope, concept, activities and partners as well as relevant activities and news throughout Europe. To serve its purpose, it is divided into two types of content:

- the “static” part, which includes project information, and
- the “dynamic” part, which is used for informing/promoting not only STEP activities but also activities and news from similar projects/networks.

Both types of content have been included in the website under certain sections. For each section, there is the possibility to add/ edit/ delete sub-sections on demand through the administrative interface. The following Chapters present the detailed STEP website’s content.

2.3.1 Home

Figure 1: STEP website - Homepage

The homepage contains an overview of the STEP website, namely project description, background and objectives, activities, latest news, recent tweets, and redirection links to partners’ official websites. There are also links to the STEP social media accounts (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, Google+), and a banner that enables visitors to subscribe in the project’s newsletter. The newsletter allows the visitor to periodically receive information regarding the progress of the project and the performed activities. At the bottom of the page the EU emblem is placed accompanied with a clear statement that the project has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 programme.

When the STEP platform is available, a banner redirecting visitors to the platform will be added at the top of the STEP homepage.

2.3.2 About STEP

This menu item provides extended information about the project and is comprised of three different sections:

Project description: This section contains an overview of the project and information regarding the duration of the project and its funding scheme.

Figure 2: STEP website - Project description section

Background & objectives: Here the problem that STEP mentions is elaborated, while the main objectives of the STEP project and the key features of the STEP platform are presented.

D7.2: Dissemination pack

The screenshot shows the 'Background & Objectives' page of the STEP website. The header includes the STEP logo and navigation links: HOME, ABOUT STEP, ABOUT US, PILOTS, DOWNLOAD AREA, USEFUL LINKS, NEWS, CONTACT. The breadcrumb trail is STEP4YOUTH > ABOUT STEP > BACKGROUND & OBJECTIVES. The main heading is 'Background & Objectives'. The text discusses the importance of youth participation in EU policy, particularly for environmental issues, and mentions the Aarhus Convention. It states that STEP aims to motivate young people to participate in decision-making through an eParticipation platform. A list of 'Key Features' includes: Social media/web mining component, Machine translation component, Text-to-Speech technology, Visualisation features, and Social media monitoring tool. A diagram at the bottom shows a person interacting with a tree-like structure of participation levels.

Figure 3: STEP website - Background & objectives

What are we doing: This section presents the seven Work Packages upon which the STEP project is built.

The screenshot shows the 'What are we doing?' page of the STEP website. The header is identical to Figure 3. The breadcrumb trail is STEP4YOUTH > ABOUT STEP > WHAT ARE WE DOING?. The main heading is 'What are we doing?'. The text states: 'The STEP project is built upon seven Work Packages:'. A list of work packages is provided: WP1 - Project Management, WP2 - Analysis and requirements, WP3 - e-Participation platform integration, WP4 - Engagement and motivation strategies for youth participation, WP5 - Pilot operation and evaluation, WP6 - Exploitation, and WP7 - Dissemination. At the bottom, there is a footer section with the STEP logo, the European Commission logo, and text stating: 'STEP aims to develop and pilot test a cloud eParticipation SaaS platform enhanced with web / social media mining, gamification, machine translation, and visualisation features, which will promote the societal and political participation of young people in the decision-making process on environmental issues.' It also mentions funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493.

Figure 4: STEP website - What are we doing?

2.3.3 About us

Partners: This section contains core information about the project partners, including their logo, their name, and their website's URL.

Figure 5: STEP website - Partners

Advisory Board: This section introduces the STEP External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) and its role in the project. The experts that have already joined EEAB are presented (name, photo, short CV).

D7.2: Dissemination pack

Figure 6: STEP website - Advisory Board

2.3.4 Pilots

In this section all information and activities relevant to the STEP pilot operations, as well as constant updates about the pilots' progress will be provided. For now, as the pilot implementation has not started yet, only short descriptions of the pilot areas are presented.

Figure 7: STEP website – Pilots

2.3.5 Download area

This section has been design to contain a variety of files for download, separated in two sections:

Deliverables: This section lists all the STEP deliverables that will be submitted to the European Commission during the project progress and enables visitors to download the public ones that have already been prepared so far.

Dissemination material: In this section visitors can find any dissemination material relevant to STEP, for instance leaflets, brochures, fact sheets, manuscripts published in journals, abstracts and articles from conference proceedings, videos etc.

2.3.6 Useful links

This section is dynamic and will be constantly updated. It provides links to projects and activities similar to STEP, regulations and laws relevant to the STEP objectives, links to the Horizon 2020 programme, and any other information that visitor may want to know.

Figure 8: STEP website - Useful links

2.3.7 Contact

This section enables visitors to send an email to the project coordinator. Visitors enter their name and email, the subject of their message and the core message. Contact information of the Project Coordinator is provided in the same section.

step

HOME ABOUT STEP ABOUT US PILOTS DOWNLOAD AREA USEFUL LINKS NEWS CONTACT

STEP4YOUTH > CONTACT Contact

Your Name (required)

Your Email (required)

Subject

Your Message

SEND

Project Coordinator: Dr. Machi Simeonidou
DRAXIS Environmental S.A., Thessaloniki, Greece
Telephone: +30 2310274566
Email: msimeonidou@draxis.gr

Figure 9: STEP website - Contact

2.3.8 Partners Area

Until now, all prepared templates of the dissemination material, as well as the final version of all STEP deliverables and any other document that should be circulated among partners were shared through Dropbox. However, all partners agreed that a private area should be built within the official STEP website. This page is now functional, but it is not publicly available. It appears in the menu bar after the user has completed the login process. Access to Partners Area is granted upon request to registered consortium members. The Partners Area includes all the information that project partners need for keeping up with the project work. Also the Partners Area includes all email distribution lists, templates for deliverables, presentations, photographs and videos relevant to the project and all the STEP finalised deliverables (public and private).

Figure 10: Login to the Partners Area

3 Leaflet

As described also in D7.1-Dissemination Plan, a first version of the STEP leaflet is already prepared and printed in a double sided three-folded A4 paper providing an overview of the project in an attractive layout. The leaflet is in English; however the pilot partners are strongly encouraged to translate the content in their language (Italian, Spanish, Catalan, Greek, Turkish) and distribute it to the pilot sites in order to maximise engagement. The leaflet’s approach (format, language, style) is user-centered.

The front page contains:

- The STEP logo, acronym and full name of the project
- The EU emblem.

The second page briefly summarises the project objectives, while the third page outlines the key features of the STEP solution. The fourth page shortly describes the five pilot areas, and in the fifth page the project partners are presented (logo, name, website, country).

Finally, the sixth page includes:

- The STEP logo and full project name
- The URL for the official project website
- The name of the STEP Facebook page
- The name of the STEP LinkedIn profile
- The name of the STEP twitter account
- The project reference number
- The type of action
- The topic under which STEP has received funding
- The duration of the project
- The contact details of the project coordinator (name, organisation, city, country, email)
- The STEP QR code that enables mobile users to quickly access the STEP website
- The EU emblem accompanied with a text stating that the project has received funding by the Horizon 2020 programme.

The leaflet is available in the project website, and it will be circulated by email or in a printed format and distributed at events.

The first STEP leaflet in its English version is presented in ANNEX A-The first version of the STEP leaflet.

4 Newsletter

The STEP newsletters will serve as a tool to communicate key updates of the project and as a channel for relevant stakeholders to be kept informed and engaged. Newsletters' content will be based upon reports filed by partners on events to which the project is presented; key updates on the development of the platform; presentations, workshops and demonstrations; reports, publications and media interest. Partners will be contacted by the WP7 leader for these contributions and/or for their approval of content. The newsletters template follows the STEP project graphical identity and clearly identifies the project as being part of an EU-funded programme.

As already planned in the DoW, a six-month newsletter will be set up. In the first six months of the project, extensive efforts have been devoted to the collection of an adequate number of potential reader's addresses. A form for easy subscription to the STEP newsletter was made also available on the STEP website.

The first STEP newsletter has been prepared, circulated among partners, the advisory board and relevant stakeholders, and advertised through social media. This first issue is presented in ANNEX B-The first issue of the STEP newsletter, and includes the following content:

- Welcome greeting by the STEP partners
- Brief presentation of the project objectives
- Explanation of the importance of young people’s participation in environmental issues
- Description of the technological aspects of the STEP platform
- Use case scenarios that clarify the impact of the project
- Presentation of the STEP partners
- Presentation of the STEP External Expert Advisory Board
- Presentation of the five STEP pilot operations
- Brief description of the issues discussed during the kick-off and the second project meetings
- Presentation of the deliverables that have been prepared and submitted to the European Commission
- Links to the STEP social media accounts
- Contact information of the Project Coordinator.

5 Video

The creation of audiovisual material for the promotion of the STEP project is of crucial importance as such tools are more attractive to young people, even to those who are not so active in social media. For the STEP project, a YouTube channel with the name “STEP Horizon2020” has been created and will be used for sharing audiovisual material relevant to the project throughout its duration.

During the first six months of the project a promotional video with general project information has been prepared and is available under the following link: https://youtu.be/5_7-EfKFI7I

6 Closing remarks

Based on the DoW, this deliverable is a result of Task 7.2-Dissemination content and activities. To summarise, the STEP website has been implemented and now is running under the URL: <http://step4youth.eu/>. It includes static and dynamic information for the website visitors as described in Chapter 2:STEP Website. The STEP website offers also a management tool among the consortium through the “Partners Area”.

The first leaflet of the STEP project has been prepared as described in Chapter 3:Leaflet and presented in ANNEX A-The first version of the STEP leaflet. Moreover, the first issue of the semi-annual project newsletter has been designed and is publicly available (Chapter 4:Newsletter), as is the first promotional video of the project (Chapter 5:Video).

ANNEX A-The first version of the STEP leaflet

GET INVOLVED

step
Societal & Political Engagement of Young People in Environmental Issues

STEP develops an eParticipation platform, based on ICT and Social Sciences technologies, that will promote the societal and political participation of young people in decision-making procedures on environmental issues.

{ STEP OBJECTIVES }

- To enable public authorities to quickly open their decision-making processes to youth
- To enable young citizens around Europe to participate in environmental decision-making
- To develop engagement and motivation strategies for increasing youth participation in environmental decision-making
- To pilot test the STEP platform
- To assess the usability and impact of the project in embedding open engagement in public sector processes

{ OBJECTIVES }

{ KEY FEATURES }

- Social media/web mining component that will provide young users with enriched information from emerging topics
- Machine translation component that will enable young users to view all the available information in their own language
- Text-to-Speech technology that will enable text to be read to users
- Visualisation features that will present the platform content in a visually stimulating way
- Social media monitoring tool that will enable public authorities to effectively plan engagement strategies for youth
- Gamification features to increase youth motivation

The STEP project is currently implemented in the following regions, but young people and stakeholders from all places and countries are welcome to participate in the pilot phase!

- The Association of the Communities of Locride area consists of 42 municipalities located in the Locride area - Italy, sharing the goal to promote development and democracy.
- Mollet del Vallès is a city of the metropolitan area of Barcelona that has won the European Green Leaf Award.
- Valdemoro city is a municipal district, located in the Southern zone of the autonomous community of Madrid, Spain.
- The Region of Crete is a second grade local self-government authority in Southern Greece.
- Hatay is one of the largest cities located in Southern Turkey and a UNESCO World City of Gastronomy.

{ PILOTS }

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DRAXIS Environmental S.A.
www.draxis.gr
Greece

CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS
www.certh.gr
Greece

LINGUATEC GMBH
www.linguatoc.de
Germany

ABERTAY UNIVERSITY DUNDEE
www.abertay.ac.uk
UK

Sant'Agata del Bianco
www.comune.santagataelbianco.rc.it
Italy

INMARK Europe
http://www.guopromark.com/
Spain

Region of Crete
www.crete.gov.gr
Greece

SAMPAS BILGİM VE İLETİŞİM SİSTEMLERİ A.Ş.
www.sampas.com.tr
Turkey

Hatay Metropolitan Municipality
www.hatay.bel.tr
Turkey

YEE-YOUTH AND ENVIRONMENT EUROPE
www.yee.net.au
Czech Republic

Ajuntament de Mollet del Vallès
www.molletvalles.cat
Spain

Kaivos Futurum AB
www.kaivosfuture.com
Sweden

Ayuntamiento de Valdemoro
www.valdemoro.es
Spain

planO2
planO2 Consulting P.C.
http://planO2.gr
Greece

{ PARTNERS }

step
Societal & Political Engagement of Young People in Environmental Issues

www.step4youth.eu | **STEP H2020 Project** | **STEP H2020 project** | **STEP_H2020**

Project reference: 649493 (H2020)
Type of action: Innovation Action
Topic: Societal and political engagement of young people and their perspectives on Europe
Duration: June 2015-November 2017 (30 months)

Project Coordinator: Dr. Machi Simionidou
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{ CONNECT WITH US }

Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation | This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

ANNEX B-The first issue of the STEP newsletter

#1
November 2015

step newsletter

Welcome!

Welcome to the first issue of the STEP Newsletter! A new issue will be published every six months from now until the end of the project with the primary aim to inform you about the progress and the results produced, as well as interesting activities undertaken throughout the duration of the STEP project. Each issue will be available in a pdf format via the project website: www.step4youth.eu.

STEP is since June 2015 in place and we, the project team, are pleased to welcome you on the pages of our first newsletter. We hope you will enjoy reading this issue and look forward to receiving your feedback.

In this issue:

- What is STEP?
- Why is participation of EU youth in environmental issues important?
- The technology behind STEP
- Why should you be interested in STEP?
- The STEP consortium
- The STEP External Expert Advisory Board
- Pilot operations
- STEP meetings
- Progress so far
- Learn more about STEP

What is STEP?

STEP aims to develop and pilot test a cloud eParticipation platform, (available as a mobile application and through a web platform) enhanced with web / social media mining, gamification, machine translation, and visualisation features, which will promote the societal and political participation of young people in the decision-making process on environmental issues.

The main component of STEP will be an eParticipation platform which will facilitate the interaction between end users (policy makers and young people), combining trend spotting and foresight with idea creation and innovation management, and will enable policy makers to analyse and discover new insights, based on well proven analytical methods.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

This publication has been produced with the assistance of the European Union. The contents of this publication is the sole responsibility of DRAXIS and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Union.

Why is participation of EU youth in environmental issues important?

Europe's future depends on its youth. Promoting youth participation is fundamental in the EU policy. Especially for environmental issues, the participation of young people in decision making is extremely important, as decisions taken now on matters such as climate change, the depletion of resources, and the loss of biodiversity will have long-term consequences that will affect the future gener-

ations. Young people will have to live longer with the consequences of current decisions, and have special concerns and responsibilities in relation to the environment. The concept of public participation is also a fundamental principle in environmental law, while the Aarhus Convention, signed by the European Community and its Member States in 1998, gives the public the right to obtain informa-

tion on environmental issues and participate in decision-making.

However, according to recent findings of the Eurobarometer, half of the young people tend to distrust the European Union. Traditional channels of representative democracy, such as voting at elections and joining political parties, only partially stimulate young people's interest in active participation.

The technology behind STEP

The STEP cloud platform will integrate the following components:

- **Social media / web mining component** that will enable young people to view personalised and enriched information relevant to the topic they are viewing, filtered through multiple social media and web sources, in one unified environment. This eliminates the need to search for content on multiple platforms, and to navigate through the overflow of information available.
- **Machine translation component** that will allow users to access content from other countries in their own language, removing language barriers and fostering cross-border interaction.
- **Text-to-Speech technology** that will enable text to be read to users, and allow also visually impaired people to use the STEP platform
- **Visualisation features** that will enable public authorities to view visual representations of data input by young users, identify patterns, spot trends, and easily analyse feedback.
- **Social media monitoring tool** that will enable public authorities to effectively plan engagement strategies for youth
- **Gamification features** which will include specific rewards (e.g. awards, badges, competitions, etc.) for increasing motivation for participation of young citizens.

Horizon 2020
European Union funding
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Why should you be interested in STEP?

STEP addresses the need of public organisations to effectively open their decision-making procedures that have an environmental impact to young people, while it enables young citizens to participate in these procedures giving them the opportunity to bring issues to the attention of policy makers.

ARE YOU BETWEEN 18 AND 29 YEARS OLD AND LOOKING FOR A REAL OPPORTUNITY TO MAKE YOUR VOICE HEARD ABOUT ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES IN YOUR AREA AND GLOBALLY?

Pantelis is a 21 years old student. He is studying philosophy at the local university and resides at the city centre where most students live. When he was teenager, he started getting involved in local environmental campaigns, protesting against harmful investments and coordinated actions with specific demands on urban environmental sustainability. Sometimes the demands reached the source of political influence meaning a small victory. But most of the times it was impossible to activate

or even approach the authorities regarding environmental matters or to be involved in the decision making processes.

Nowadays, Pantelis is still an active citizen with environmental concerns and operates through the STEP platform. Although, his time is limited due to part-time work in a small café, he manages to stay informed and constantly updated on the environmental issues through the social media feeds connected to STEP. Now he can easily find information about poli-

cy making decisions, expresses his opinion, and motivates his fellow students or even his clients to play environmental games in order to excite their environmental awareness. Additionally, he can perform both as part of a proactive team coordinating arguments and actions using STEP and as individual young citizen receiving feedback from the decision makers. Also, he finds exciting the cross-border interaction with other European stakeholders, provided by STEP in his own language, and prefers to engage with this wider environmental approach.

ARE YOU A POLICY MAKER TRYING TO QUICKLY OPEN YOUR DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES TO YOUNG PEOPLE?

Ms. Rodriguez is the Mayor of a big municipality in Barcelona. Among her other duties, she has to run various types of decision-making processes, including those concerning controversial local environmental issues. These days, her main concern is the demolition of an amusement park located in the region of her municipality, so that a mall can be erected. However, this park is the green spot of her municipality and the location where the majority of young citizens spend their time, joking, hiking, or even enjoy-

ing the sunshine. As she expected, the announcement of the demolition of the park has aroused many conflicts in the community, with the younger ones protesting and demanding to take part in the decision.

The Mayor believes herself that the best solution is to pose the issue for public consultation, but a solution has to be found immediately, because the owners of the potential mall are pressing her to accelerate the procedure. Moreo-

ver, she can't afford the risk of the potential budget spent and political costs of public participation with the conventional means, including the loss of administrative and political control.

The STEP platform seems attractive to her as it is specially designed for young people aiming to increase their political and social engagement with the usage of social media and participatory tools. She also needs tools to enhance

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the trust, especially of the young, in decision making procedures in order to ensure accountability and social harmony. Furthermore, the STEP platform will help her to

interpret the young citizens' opinion via the visual representation of results which enable her to view patterns and spot trends, facilitating decision making. Hopefully,

this new STEP solution will help her meet the demanding targets of the community involving the youth in political activities with the limited resources available.

The STEP consortium

DRAXIS

The STEP External Expert Advisory Board

The External Expert Advisory Board comprises representatives from organisations relevant to youth participation, environment, policy making, data protection, and social media. Their role will be to participate in workshops in which they will review the project activities and outcomes, identify

the strong and weak points with respect to the objectives of the project and the applications of the results, and provide recommendations. For more information on the members of the Board please visit the STEP website (www.step4youth.eu).

Pilot operations

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STEP meetings

1&2 / 6 / 2015

STEP kick-off meeting took place in Thessaloniki, Greece on the 1st and 2nd of June 2015. All partners were represented and contributed with ideas and expertise to ensure the smooth implementation of the crucial first semester of the project.

5&6 / 10 / 2015

The STEP partners met for the **2nd project meeting** in Istanbul, Turkey on 5th and 6th October 2015. The discussions focused mainly on several technical issues regarding the integration of the STEP platform, as well as on the preparation of the pilot implementations foreseen (current state analysis, barriers, opportunities, solutions, etc.). Moreover, the work done on user needs and on mapping of decision making procedures was presented.

Progress so far

Until now, the following deliverables have been prepared and submitted to the European Commission:

- "D1.1-Project Management Handbook": summarises all the organisational structure, operating procedures and management tools of the project.
- "D1.2-Minutes of 1st Advisory Board meeting": provides an overview of the most important points discussed during the 1st External Expert Advisory Board meeting of the project.
- "D2.1-Report on decision-making procedures": maps decision making procedures on environmental issues so as to enable the STEP partners to get an insight in the regulatory environment, the stakeholders involved and the potential fields of e-participation applications.
- "D2.2-Report on users' needs and technical requirements": presents the research activities conducted for the definition of user and technical requirements for the STEP platform.
- "D6.1-1st IPR strategy report": provides an overview of the main aspects of IPR that need to be taken into account in the STEP project.
- "D7.1-1st Dissemination Plan": sets the dissemination strategy that will be followed and elaborates the project's dissemination activities that will be executed throughout the duration of the project.

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Learn more about STEP

Visit now the STEP website www.step4youth.eu. There you can find any information relevant to STEP you are looking for: the project objectives, updates from the pilots, partners' contact details, interesting news, public deliverables, dissemination material, and much more...

Also join STEP in social media to be constantly updated about all project news and activities.

: STEP H2020 Project

: STEP H2020 project

: @STEP_H2020

: Step Horizon2020

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